

g2) the upper part of Aristotelous St.(its lower part favours only the inhabitant movement)

g3) the axes of St. Sophia-Acheropoetous as well as Ionos Dragoumis and Vas.Sophia's Sts. (lines 4,16)

g4) the old administration centres

g5) the old Greek churches already provided with high values in the neoclassical plan.

h) Areas of high choice values are most of the old markets (especially Ladadika) in their heart, while the 1917-designed markets afford such values only along their borders (Vlalis-Vatikiotis,Pazarakia).

Areas of low IM and MI values are

a) Rotonda-Hippodrome cluster

b) the old tertiary sector in "Malta" area

c) most of the old Turkish public buildings.

h) With respect to "Ano-Polis", the major achievement of the plan, beyond the high values along the frontiers, is the high inhabitant-movement route developed up to the northern frontiers penetrating its heart (lines 10,11,20,22,33,58).These lines do not involve the major public buildings or open spaces of the area, but only some of the commercial uses. If considered as a separate subsystem, there is a remarkable overlap between the two high inhabitant movement routes (maps 49,50). The frontiers have become even more dense and the high movement interface along them is almost continual. The internal routes also carry the main public facilities and commercial activities (lines 31,24,14,3,23,20,17,25,30,11,6,36,5,9,13,27,20,7), but not the main open

spaces or old public buildings; very few old Greek churches are on high inhabitant movement lines. The integration and choice maps superimposed (maps 42 and 49), there is a major overlap concerning the two major links along the borders and a third one penetrating the area's heart, all three of them of high movement interface values. Therefore, the system not only becomes more accessible from the outside, but it also permits strangers to traverse it at its parts.

Concluding, inhabitant movement and movement interface continuity with respect to the carrier is enhanced.

The system considered internally, the IM and MI are more than previously uniformly, rationally and symmetrically distributed. Moreover, the city's geometrical axes, the major diagonals and main streets of the integrating "supergrid" are provided with high IM and MI values.

The C.B.D., the old and the new administration areas, the commerce along the main routes perpendicular or parallel to the coast, the upper part of Aristotelous St., the major axes of St.Sophia-Acheropeoetus and Vas.Sophia's St. are provided with high both IM and MI values. Instead, the old C.B.D and the 1917-designed markets are provided with low values.

St.Sophia-Acheropeoetus cluster affords high IM and MI values, while Aristotelous St. and Rotonda-hippodrome clusters remain on low values.

Most of the old Greek public buildings once converted to mosques and revealed by the neoclassical plan are transformed into free-standing buildings with high IM and MI values. In contrast, the Greek public buildings not favoured by the Neoclassical plan gained very low values under the Modern plan. The public buildings of the other two ethnicities were provided with the lowest possible values; the same applies to the

public open spaces of all three ethnicities.

"Ano-Polis" became more accessible from the outside and traversable at all its width up to the city's northern frontiers (high IM and MI values); along these routes commerce is mostly encouraged; the major public buildings and open spaces remain segregated.

6.4 The late 1980s Plan (Axial map 1.4)

6.4.1. Integration (maps as in 6.3.1)

The plan strengthens and stabilises the links with the carrier.

In the core there are now articulated refined uses of the tertiary sector, recreation and cultural activities.

The extension of C.B.D. westwards occupies some of the most segregated areas at the western borders of the city-within the-walls.

E.P.A. reallocates retailing and workshops at the western part of the metropolitan area, not equally accessible.

The pedestrianisation of Nikis blrd (highly accessible) is expected to draw the flow of pedestrians from the major promenades referred above and lead them to the proposed recreational and cultural centre eastward the White Tower. Nevertheless, all three promenades remain on low-accessibility lines.

In "Ano-Polis" proposed major pedestrian networks, public services and commercial activities are mostly allocated along the highly accessible routes. Retailing centre (workshops and light manufacturing close to the traditional handicraft) is allocated along a dense pedestrian route that seems to be highly accessible. Some other central-area functions (e.g. youth hostels) are found in highly segregated clusters which is rather

positive, helping to eliminate "deserted" areas. Some "listed" routes are found to be linked to the most accessible streets: strangers will find their way around rather easily in order to visit the most interesting parts of the area. Besides, the flow of people will penetrate smoothly its deep parts, since most of these routes traverse highly segregated areas. A weak point is that they do not involve the major public open spaces (except of Kallitheas sq.).

6.4.2. Control (C) -Intelligibility (I) (maps as in 6.3.2)

Control and integration cores are largely identical concerning the links with the carrier, the four internal major diagonals and the vertical main commercial streets.

The extension of C.B.D. does not gain equally high control values compared to the old C.B.D.

Areas designated to accommodate primarily upper-class housing gain high C values.

The three "promenades" except that of Aristotelous St. are on high C values up to "Ano-Polis" and they can be expected to provide pedestrians with a certain amount of information about the urban lay-out at its perceivable scale.

The movement along the frontiers has many parts of high C values, whereas in the corpus of "Ano-Polis" these values are scattered hardly coinciding with the identified "listed" routes. Furthermore, most of the proposed central-area functions are on low-control-value lines.

The extension of C.B.D. westwards is penetrated by three parallel, high-value streets, but the area does not afford as good intelligibility values as

the old C.B.D. does. The main difference is that in the old C.B.D. high values penetrate and involve the whole area providing visitors and inhabitants with a clear image of the city-centre while in its extension the analogous lines traverse it partially and linearly.

The intelligibility values of the four "monumental promenades" are low.

The major routes to "Ano-Polis", mostly identical to the vehicle traffic routes, have high values at their lowest parts: visitors along Olympiados and Athinas Sts will find it difficult to traverse "Ano-Polis" through the designated pedestrian and "listed" routes. In the area itself and along streets where commerce is expected to develop, there is a lack of high I values and the same applies to most of the proposed "listed" routes.

6.4.3. Choice (CH) -Movement Interface (MI)

(maps as in 6.3.3)

In Lower City the identification of choice and integration cores is accompanied by the allocation of activities along main arteries; the inhabitant movement is condensed along them, while other places in the heart of the districts are left excessively "quiet".

The three "promenades", except that of the galerian complex, are on routes of high choice values: inhabitant-movement is dense along them.

In "Ano-Polis" high choice-value lines, hardly forming continual routes, are identified to the high-density vehicle routes. It is positive that they involve the two major squares of the area. Since the proposed "listed" routes are linked with high-value lines, it is most possible that the flow of inhabitants will spread along them.

Most of the proposed uses concern mainly city-quarters and not the city

as a whole; it could be expected that their allocation should not meet the existing high movement interface lines. Since this is not the case, it can be anticipated that the heart of the quarters will be deprived from the dense inhabitant movement, while major streets will be over-condensed.

The C.B.D. extension westwards is provided with lower MI values than those of the C.B.D. within-the-walls and this again can be expected to cause deserted environment in out-of-work hours.

Two out of the three monumental promenades are of low MI values (St. Sophia-Acheropoetous is exempted).

In "Ano-Polis" high MI values are more identical to the main vehicle-oriented routes and less to the proposed pedestrian network.

CHAPTER VII: DISCUSSION AND INTERPRETATION

7. Discussion and Interpretation

In the 1890 Plan the limited and high global-value entrances from the carrier indicate that the city worked mainly as a self-contained, unique and largely independent system where accessibility was drawn and controlled in the most public spaces of the city; they also indicate the limited role in "transpatial" links that the city maintained with other urban systems.

The deformation of the grid is maximum compared to the later plans.

The core integrated the parts of the city to a central structure providing a domain where people were aware of each other's presence and interacted, while it left to the most segregated clusters the main residential areas. Besides, it integrated the major Turkish public buildings and open spaces and left out the Greek and Jewish ones, as well as the ancient "Agora" or roman "Forum".

Moreover, the core was much more concerned with linking market areas and commercial streets with the carrier, than distributing high spatial values internally and especially the residential areas. Besides, dispersed and segregated areas afforded high local values: inhabitants conceptualised and used an urban space entirely different from that of strangers, and different ethnicities were provided with different spatial values.

Therefore, "through" and "to-movement" were encouraged in market areas, the commercial streets and administration centre-the most homogeneous and "transpatial" parts of the city. In these areas there were some pockets with low global but high local values and this proves that these functions were largely city-and not region-based.

The harbour area was mainly accessible and intelligible by strangers and

to a less extent by inhabitants.

In Turkish quarters the overlap between the city's core and the Turkish one integrates the major administrative centre and public services of the city. Moreover, there was a smooth distribution of high spatial-values routes from the city-core to the quarters (especially the low-income ones in Lower City): inhabitants and visitors perceived these areas and moved through them more easily than in any other part of the city. Along these routes there were articulated the major public buildings and public open spaces of the community. In "Ano-Polis" the above attributes were substantially decreased and this can be attributed, beyond any geomorphological reasons, to the fact that there resided the upper class Turks that desired isolation from the rest of the city's population.

Therefore, the Turkish quarters were the least homogeneous and the most "transpatial" subsystem after market areas tending to maintain links and possibly control the overall urban structure.

The Jews allocated along their high-values lines commercial activities and to a less extent their socio-cultural centres. Strangers could not perceive and were discouraged to enter Jewish areas. In contrast, inhabitants were provided with a dense network of high local spatial-value thoroughfares. The area of the city's tertiary sector ("Malta") was provided with high local and low global spatial values.

The Jewish quarters were more homogeneous than the Turkish ones, maintaining strong links only with the market areas, not easily accessible from the outside, realising strong boundaries with the other ethnicities and internal hierarchies. The spatial attributes compared quantitatively, they were much lower than those of the Turkish areas.

Greek quarters were the most homogeneous ones, with strong boundaries, hierarchies and disruptions from the high-values lines of the

major core. When Greek and Turkish quarters were neighbours, interlinks were discouraged and boundaries and internal hierarchies got stronger. The scarce public buildings and public open spaces were on lines of low, zero or even minus local and global values. The hierarchy in this case transcended even the private landownership. In contrast, the superimposed Turkish public buildings were on lines with high spatial values. This subsystem had the lowest spatial values, it was the most bounded of all subsystems and it worked strongly on the correspondence model emphasising the spatial links in the community based on proximity and ethnical identity.

The continual routes of high local and global spatial properties distributed from the major "supergrid" to the Turkish quarters and the disruption of this continuity toward the Jewish and Greek quarters and furthermore, the low values of these attributes in Jewish quarters and their almost absence in Greek ones, indicate that the system had got its four major subsystems with different internal structure, codes of relations to each other and degree of "transpatiality". The boundaries of each subsystem reached their climax in the Greek quarters and their minimum in Turkish ones and market areas.

The Turkish community seemed to be the most "transpatial" whereas the Greek the most spatial one.

The 1891 plan did not affect the global properties of the previous plan, except of increasing slightly its heterogeneity. It improved the local properties in some of the Jewish quarters by linking them directly with the market and Greek areas. Again, the redesign of these quarters provided with better values the commercial streets and not their socio-cultural centres.

The 1917 plan altered consistently the spatial structure of the city in both global and local scales.

The links with the carrier, beyond their multiplication, were provided with exceptionally high global values.

The deformation of the grid was substantially reduced except in "Ano-Polis" that remained close to the morphology of the "organic" cities. The gridiron plan made morphologically much more homogeneous the various city-parts.

The accessibility core did not form any more a closed, compact corpus in the centre, but it developed strong links with the carrier; furthermore, beyond inferring visitors to the city's heart and operating as a strong integrator, it integrated uses allocated out of the frontiers, but necessary for the function of the city. It also carried the central-area functions of an urban system much broader than that of the pre-1917 plans.

With regards to the internal movement of visitors, it enhanced the possibility strangers to perceive and move around a broader area, reaching and even transcending purely residential areas. The above, combined with the absence of any clusters of high values, indicate that the system had acquired substantially improved global and local properties. Besides, smooth distribution of values all over the spatial structure indicates its improved homogeneity.

Visitors and inhabitants were equally and easily accessed to the administration centre, the main commercial streets and the city's expanding tertiary sector. More precisely, the old and the newly-traced commercial streets and wholesale markets gained high local and global spatial values, whereas the newly-designed markets and the cluster with the pre-1917 tertiary sector acquired very low spatial values.

Most of the major old Greek public buildings and open spaces, by

acquiring their initial or similar use, they became organising elements of the plan itself and articulated to the highest spatial-values lines. In contrast, the remained Turkish and Jewish public buildings became even locally of lower spatial values than they had in the pre-1917 plans. The three newly-designed monumental wholenesses afforded low values except of the wholeness of St. Sophia-Acheropoeotous that acquired high local values. Especially Aristotelous St., provided with low spatial values, constitutes a contradiction of the plan itself, since it was expected to gain a significant flow of people.

The residential areas had substantially increased their local and global properties, thus, the "transpatial" links among inhabitants and between strangers and inhabitants being improved significantly. Continuities of these high global-value lines involved major old Greek public buildings and open spaces. Ranking according to income (which is proved to be the determinant factor in the post-1917 city), upper-class areas were provided with higher spatial values than lower-income ones.

"Ano-Polis" (that turned to a low-income inner-city area) was provided with substantially increased spatial values along its borders, but not equally high values in its heart. The area remained very close to the previous "organic" structure of the city and low-income Greeks were marginalised there.

The mid 1970s plan had quantitatively reduced the global and local properties of the 1971 plan, although it distributed them rationally, homogeneously and more symmetrically.

The links with the carrier were multiplied and provided with higher values transforming the city within-the-walls to a subsystem with the highest genetic code of a much broader arrangement: the city's parts not

only became highly accessible from its core, but also directly accessible from the carrier, acquiring weaker boundaries and even weaker internal hierarchies than the neoclassical plan.

Central-area functions that gained all the more better local and global spatial values were the commercial activities, still a small part of the 1917-designed market areas, most of the rapidly expanding C.B.D. and the administration centre.

The old wholesale markets and the major commercial streets perpendicular to the coast acquired better local properties and this indicates that commerce competed in importance with the developing C.B.D. Instead, the pre-1917 C.B.D. and the 1917-designed markets were provided with very low values. Therefore, strangers visited the city for commercial, administration and tertiary sector activities that were allocated mixedly in the city's lay-out, while major zoning schemes were not frequently visited by both strangers and inhabitants.

The harbour and the traditional food and clothe-markets remained with low values, but nevertheless, better than the 1917-designed markets.

The links with "Ano-Polis" acquired high global and local properties: the area itself became more homogeneous and accessible from the carrier as well as in its heart due to its penetration by major routes with high spatial properties linking the frontiers with Lower city. The highest-values routes carried commercial activities, while the major old public buildings, public open spaces and recreation centres remained in low-values areas: the area improved the values of its commercial streets at the expense of its public services and open public space facilities. Quantitatively, it remained with the lowest values compared to the other city-parts.

The rapid expansion of C.B.D. that tended to occupy the whole city-core, pushed housing to the lowest spatial-values areas. Along this process,

high-income areas acquired much better spatial values than low-income ones.

In the late 1980s plan the city develops as an even more specialised and refined focal point of the broader metropolitan area, the links with the carrier being stabilised by the strategic allocation of different central-area functions.

High global values are acquired by administration, commerce, recreation and cultural activities.

The extension of C.B.D. westwards affords lower values than the C.B.D. within-the-walls.

Retailing and workshops upwards Egnatia St., reallocated close to the western frontiers, acquire lower spatial values.

Monumental promenades are provided with low global and high local values: they are perceived and accessed only by inhabitants. Moreover, their links with Niki's blvd and the designated recreation centre at its eastern edge provides the whole network with rather low spatial values.

Some of the proposed uses serving the city-quarters are found along main arteries with exceptionally high global values while the heart of these quarters is left with excessively low ones.

Toward "Ano-Polis" the main routes have low global values; strangers can not perceive and be easily accessed in the heart of the area itself. In contrast, the main vehicle-traffic routes are provided with high spatial values. The proposed pedestrian networks along "listed" routes although not provided with high values, are directly linked with the high-values routes; moreover, they encourage the continual flow of strangers and inhabitants along them through the strategic allocation of central-area functions. Some of the proposed uses are found in the heart of the most

segregated areas and this is rather positive for the enhancement of interaction of people there. High inhabitant movement and movement interface routes are not identical to the highly constituted ones and this is ,again, rather positive, for spreading broadly the flow of people in the area. The major public open spaces remain on low global and high local spatial values, being almost exclusively used by inhabitants.

The transformation of the city's links with respect to the carrier can be attributed to the fact that

a) in the pre-1917 period the city developed as a self-contained sociopolitical structure getting prosperous by trading and largely maintaining its independence from the carrier;

b) in the 1917-1975 period it developed as a thriving centre of commerce, manufacture and industry and this led to an increase of the transportation networks: the plan was much more concerned with the multiplication of the links with the carrier, than the improvement of the internal to the system spatial values;

c) in the late 1980s the city is a centre of a whole region with multiplied, beyond its conventional links, its "transpatial" and intangible channels of communication with respect to the outside world.

In the pre-1917 plans each ethnicity was provided with different grid patterns and spatial heterogeneity. Least gridiron were the Greek areas-the Greeks were the most oppressed community- and most gridiron the Turkish and market areas -the rulers had no reasons to exclude strangers other than those of "prestige" ("Ano-Polis"), or cultural principles. In

Jewish quarters the deformation of the grid has to be attributed more to their cultural principles and less to their relation with the rulers. Compared to the later plans, the "organic" one was the least gridiron and this indicates that the communities tried to avoid to be controlled by their rulers.

The Neoclassical plan achieved a substantial degree of morphological homogeneity through the increase of the gridiron design: it was addressed to the substantially homogenised Greek population of the city.

The Modern plan enhanced this homogeneity through the further increase of the gridiron design (the most gridiron plan of the city): it increased the rationalisation, control and exploitation of urban space and land-use allocation.

The Post-modern plan is rather concerned with the embodiment of the "organic" and neoclassical typologies in the contemporary plan attempting to provide the city with high spatial values through "collage" processes and redistributive mechanisms. Moreover, increased heterogeneity means lack of superordinate control.

The pre-1917 plans afforded low global and local spatial values, the highest of them distributed between their socio-cultural centres and market areas.

The Neoclassical plan increased substantially these values, shifting the interest to commercial areas.

In the Modern plan, although these properties were internally more homogeneously developed than ever, they were reduced quantitatively: city-districts gained almost equally low values, considerably differentiated according to income of their residing social classes. Again, the primary concern of the plan had been to provide administration, retailing and

tertiary sector with the highest values, applying on them (and in residential areas) rigid zoning principles.

Post-modern plan attempts mainly to increase the city's spatial properties in all residential areas irrespectively to income.

The pre-1917 plans provided market areas with the highest global and local values compared to the other central-area functions.

The Neoclassical plan did not involve the designed markets in its highest spatial values (as the neoclassical ideology suggested), these activities being more or less isolated from the other central area functions.

The Modern plan, by intensifying the application of the gridiron and zoning system in these areas, provided them with even lower spatial values.

Post-modern plan proposes commercial routes involving whole market areas in order to increase movement interface along them, and thus, enhance the safety and diversity of public spaces.

Market areas and commercial streets had been the public space in the pre-1917 city, the most "transpatial" subsystem maintaining the mixing mechanism for all three ethnicities, the area of interaction and exchange. Both Neoclassical and Modern plans favoured retailing along commercial streets at the expense of the traditionally developed market areas ; the attribute of the latter as places of frequent movement interface and interaction that guarantees the safety and diversity of the urban space was understood and used by the Post-modern plan.

In the pre-1917 plans the "hybrid" C.B.D. was rather isolated and only the Jews were easily accessed there: Jews controlled the market and the flow of currency in the city linked with banks and other monetary

institutions in "Malta" area.

The tertiary sector and all three zones of C.B.D. in the Neoclassical plan did not acquire substantially higher spatial values, although this was one of the plan's primary objects.

In the Modern plan the C.B.D. acquired the highest spatial values of the system: in modern ages, the city was transcended by the capitalist mode of production when the growth of the tertiary sector was maximised.

Post-modern plan legitimises the trends for its expansion even out of the city walls; since physical proximity has been replaced by easy accessibility to the intangible channels of communication, C.B.D. and accessibility core need not be any more identical.

C.B.D. spatial values compared among themselves and with other uses, reveal their increasing importance from the Neoclassical plan and onwards. Housing, commerce and administration that prevailed in the pre-1917 plans seem to retreat remarkably afterwards, gradually replaced by the C.B.D. transforming the city-core into a mono-functional arrangement. The contradiction of the Post-modern plan is that while it tries to mix C.B.D. with other land-uses in the city within-the-walls, it applies rather zoning principles in its western extension.

In the pre-1917 plans the articulation of the socio-cultural centres to the city's lay-out obeyed to the laws of the ethnicities' cultural structure and the interrelationships between them, providing the communities with ethnical identity, coherence and social integration. In the multi-ethnic social structure the ruling ethnicity achieved their prevalence over the minorities through the control of urban space and the strategic allocation of its public buildings and open spaces.

The excessively high or high global values that the old Greek public

buildings and wholenesses gained under the Neoclassical plan can be easily attributed to the fact that the plan was addressed only to the Greek community and it was their socio-cultural centres that it tried to provide with high spatial values. By the same means, the plan tried to eliminate the ethnical identity of the other communities by degrading the spatial values of their socio-cultural centres. Nevertheless, by failing to provide with high spatial values the three "monumental wholenesses", the Neoclassical plan provided the Greek community with its ethnical identity symbolically rather than syntactically. Moreover, the same areas were proposed to host land-uses assigned to serve the growing tertiary sector, political, administrative and socio-cultural activities serving, thus, the upper levels of the Greek society.

The Modern plan further rationalised the urban space serving the interests of these very same social classes: almost all the old public buildings had been substantially deprived of all high spatial values and in their best they shifted from socio-cultural centres of the Greek community to free-standing artifacts. It is the period with the major disruptions from the history of the city.

In Post-modern plans the remaining old Greek socio-cultural centres are involved in major pedestrian routes or "monumental promenades" linking the old and the new public buildings to a continual pedestrian network close to the most accessible streets of the area and this will rather draw large amounts of visitors and inhabitants along them. Besides, most of the proposed central area functions are found either along the most accessible routes or close to them. The plans attempt redistribution of the flow of movement in the city, emphasising the continuity of the historical phases that the city transcended and elimination of any kind of highly segregated clusters. Along this process, an overwhelming emphasis is set on

recreational activities as the means to fill the gaps between the historical elements and act as "magnets" drawing the flow of people along them. Nevertheless, there is the danger the city to develop as a museum of its past and not as a lively place for its present: in other words, the allocation and mix of the vital to the function of the city land-uses could be reconsidered.

As far as social organisation and distribution of different groups is concerned, it has been found that the phenomenon of segregation has before and after 1917 reversed its meaning, as low-income people from 1917 and onwards inhabit the previous domain of the ruling group and upper-class people now occupy some of the old area of the oppressed Greek minority. The location of these groups in these areas could be related to the new priorities of the upper class which preferred to be close to the centre of economic activity and to the disadvantaged position of "Ano-Polis", due to its relative unaccessibility by car.

In the Modern plan, the limits between different social-class residential areas were realised more profoundly than ever; the poor were pushed at the most deprived and segregated areas while the prevalence of the rich in the city-core was all the more strengthened.

Both Neoclassical and modern plans differentiated either implicitly or explicitly residential areas from central-area functions realising largely zoning principles. In contrast, Post-modern plans aim primarily at the mixture of the above uses and moreover, the articulation of housing in the old "down-town" area. They set a series of mechanisms prohibiting or encouraging land-use allocation, controlling thus, the flow of people in the city.

As it was expected, the 1890 plan is a strong genotype (g-model) with attributes of low "distributedness" and high "non-distributedness", working on strong correspondences and weak non-correspondences between its social groups and spatial categories, a homeostatic structure with strong internal rules safeguarding its reproduction over time.

In the purely residential areas of all three ethnicities non-"distributedness" implied asymmetry or, more simply, a "tree-like" structure forming a "no-neighbours" model in terms of links between "ethnoquarters" where the syntax of boundaries, spaces and "permeabilities" guaranteed that the conduct of every day life would exclude accidental contact with "neighbours as neighbours" (i.e. Greeks and Turks).

As a result of the increased internal segregation of the ethnicities' built structure, inhabitants did not relate to each other as inhabitants other than in the small ethnical groups, while they never interfaced strangers in their role as inhabitants because of the depth of their public space from the most integrating parts; and strangers never penetrated to the ethnicities' residential areas, because of the depth from the carrier. Therefore, the plan reveals a society working on strong mechanical and weak organic solidarities.

The 1891 plan was expected to work on strong correspondences and weak non-correspondences, enhancing locally the "distributedness" of some quarters. It was the strongest ever evolved phenotype of the 1890 plan. The "homeorysis" phase it represented, did not pose a new code of spatial attributes and, hence, it did not lead to a new morphogenesis.

The major "homeorysis" that transcended the political and social structure of the city catalysed by the fire in 1917 led to the morphogenesis of a new spatial system, the neoclassical plan.

This plan acquired substantially different and quantitatively increased local and global properties; it can be considered as another genotype working largely on non-correspondence principles between social groups and spatial categories, based on "transpatiality" with weak boundaries and increased links with the carrier. While becoming a subsystem of a much broader spatial arrangement, it developed internally strong, confining within the walls its highest first and second order spatial properties. It endeavoured to design a whole city according to a single set of principles and in that sense, it paved the way for modernism.

The Modern plan is a phenotype of the neoclassical one (p-model), working on the limit between "homeostasis" and "homeorysis" phases and developing parallel to the drastically changing social structure. It works largely on the principle of non-correspondence, based on "transpatiality" and even more increased links with the carrier. Its homogeneity is maximum compared to all other plans. This p-model altered drastically some of the key-elements and principles of the Neoclassical plan setting under threat its quantitative and qualitative generative spatial values; for, by increasing its global values, it reduced the qualitative attributes of the initial genotype and by enhancing its "transpatiality", it was left with lower internal -especially local- properties. The boundaries and internal hierarchies differentiated land-uses providing the rich with the highest accessibility to the city-centre and also the highest spatial values in their residential areas.

Post-Modern plans are an effort to mix the neoclassical and organic typologies (g-models) with the Modern plan (p-model) aiming at the principle of "structured non-correspondences". The strategic allocation of central-area functions is employed in order to achieve "transpatiality", openness, lack of boundaries, distributed and symmetric attributes of the

spatial structure and if possible, its corresponding social one.

The two strong genotypes developed and transformed radically the city's spatial structure when the social structure had changed drastically. The three phenotypes developed in 1891, modern and post-modern ages are strong, but not enough to alter the systems' internal codes and produce a new system, since they have been produced by the very same social structure with their corresponding genotypes.

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